

Table S3. Scoring of morphological characters for statistical analysis

Strain number	Other strain number(s)	Species	Colour obverse			Colour reverse			Texture	
			Scoring	Colour name ¹	Colour code ¹	Scoring	Colour name ¹	Colour code ¹	Scoring	Kind
CCF 6575	CLIS 3036/16	<i>T. interdigitale</i>	2	yellowish white	3a2	2	yolk yellow	4b8	1	cottony
CCF 6577	DMF 3680/14	<i>T. interdigitale</i>	2	yellowish white	3a2	3	yellowish brown	5d8	1	cottony
CCF 6583	L 307/15	<i>T. interdigitale</i>	1	white	1a1	1	yellowish white	3a2	2	velvety
CLIS 1142/15		<i>T. interdigitale</i>	2	yellowish white	4a2	3	rust brown	6e8	2	velvety
CLIS 1161/15		<i>T. interdigitale</i>	2	yellowish white	4a2	3	yellowish brown	5e8	1	cottony
CLIS 2234/15		<i>T. interdigitale</i>	1	white	1a1	1	pale yellow	4a3	2	velvety
CLIS 3573/16		<i>T. interdigitale</i>	1	white	1a1	3	honey yellow	5d6	2	velvety
CLIS 3957/15		<i>T. interdigitale</i>	1	white	1a1	3	clay	5d5	1	cottony
CLIS 4678/15		<i>T. interdigitale</i>	1	white	1a1	2	oxide yellow	5c7	2	velvety
CLIS 6575/15		<i>T. interdigitale</i>	1	white	1a1	2	brownish yellow	5c8	2	velvety
CLIS 8227/15		<i>T. interdigitale</i>	1	white	1a1	2	brownish yellow	5c8	2	velvety
CLIS 9064/16		<i>T. interdigitale</i>	1	white	1a1	1	pale yellow	4a3	2	velvety
D 15/17		<i>T. interdigitale</i>	1	white	1a1	3	linoleum brown	5e7	2	velvety
D 152/15		<i>T. interdigitale</i>	1	white	1a1	3	honey yellow	5d6	1	cottony
D 167/15		<i>T. interdigitale</i>	1	white	1a1	3	clay	5d5	1	cottony
D 180/16		<i>T. interdigitale</i>	2	yellowish white	4a2	3	light brown	6d8	2	velvety
D 296/15		<i>T. interdigitale</i>	2	yellowish white	4a2	2	apricot (yellow)	5b6	2	velvety
D 4/16		<i>T. interdigitale</i>	2	yellowish white	4a2	2	oxide yellow	5c7	3	granular
D 437/14		<i>T. interdigitale</i>	1	white	1a1	2	oxide yellow	5c7		
D 437/17		<i>T. interdigitale</i>	1	white	1a1	3	yellowish brown	5e8	1	cottony
D 480/15		<i>T. interdigitale</i>	1	white	1a1	3	clay	5d5	3	granular
D 5/17		<i>T. interdigitale</i>	1	white	1a1	1	pale yellow	4a3		
D 512/15		<i>T. interdigitale</i>	1	white	1a1	2	amber yellow	4b6	3	granular
D 515/15		<i>T. interdigitale</i>	1	white	1a1	2	popeian yellow	5c6	2	velvety
D 527/15		<i>T. interdigitale</i>	2	yellowish white	4a2	2	oxide yellow	5c7	2	velvety
D 586/16		<i>T. interdigitale</i>	1	white	1a1	3	yellowish brown	5d8	2	velvety
D 613/17		<i>T. interdigitale</i>	1	white	1a1	2	chamcis	4c5	3	granular
D 618/15		<i>T. interdigitale</i>	1	white	1a1	3	dark brown	7f8	2	velvety
D 624/15		<i>T. interdigitale</i>	1	white	1a1	2	oxide yellow	5c7	1	cottony
D 743/16		<i>T. interdigitale</i>	1	white	1a1	3	linoleum brown	5e7	2	velvety
D 767/16		<i>T. interdigitale</i>	1	white	1a1	2	amber yellow	4b6	1	cottony
D 809/15		<i>T. interdigitale</i>	1	white	1a1	1	pale yellow	4a3	2	velvety
D 812/15		<i>T. interdigitale</i>	1	white	1a1	1	pastel yellow	3a4	1	cottony
DMF 1069/15		<i>T. interdigitale</i>	1	white	1a1	1	oxide yellow	5c7	2	velvety
DMF 2715/14		<i>T. interdigitale</i>	2	yellowish white	3a2	3	honey yellow	5d6	1	cottony
DMF 3025/14		<i>T. interdigitale</i>	1	white	1a1	2	chamcis	4c5	2	velvety
L 1095/14		<i>T. interdigitale</i>	2	yellowish white/pa	2a2	3	clay	5d5	3	granular
L 1334/15		<i>T. interdigitale</i>	1	white	1a1	3	cognac	6e7	3	granular
L 1475/14		<i>T. interdigitale</i>	1	white	1a1	2	maize yellow	4a6	2	velvety
L 244/16		<i>T. interdigitale</i>	1	white	1a1	2	popeian yellow	5c6	1	cottony
L 263/17		<i>T. interdigitale</i>	1	white	1a1	2	golden	4c6	2	velvety
L 505/15		<i>T. interdigitale</i>	1	white	1a1	2	reddish golden	6c7	1	cottony
L 601/15		<i>T. interdigitale</i>	1	white	1a1	1	pale yellow	4a3	1	cottony
ME 1042/14		<i>T. interdigitale</i>	1	white	1a1	1	pale yellow	4a3	1	cottony
ME 1137/14		<i>T. interdigitale</i>	1	white	1a1	1	pastel yellow	3a4	1	cottony
ME 2/15		<i>T. interdigitale</i>	2	yellowish white/pa	1a1	2	topaz	5c5	2	velvety
ME 517/15		<i>T. interdigitale</i>	1	white	1a1	1	pastel yellow	3a4	1	cottony
ME 602/15		<i>T. interdigitale</i>	2	yellowish white	1a2	1	light yellow	4a4	1	cottony
ME 756/15		<i>T. interdigitale</i>	1	white	1a1	2	greyish orange	5b5	3	granular
ME 900/15		<i>T. interdigitale</i>	2	pastel yellow	3a4	3	yellowish brown	5d8	2	velvety
ME 918/14		<i>T. interdigitale</i>	2	pale yellow	3a3	2	banana/chinese yellow	4b7	1	cottony
ME 949/14		<i>T. interdigitale</i>	1	white	1a1	3	dark brown	7f8	1	cottony
PL 1165/16		<i>T. interdigitale</i>	2	yellowish white/pa	2a2	3	yellowish brown	5d8	2	velvety

LEGEND: Scoring system for statistical analysis		
Colour obverse	Colour reverse	Texture
1a1=1	3a2=1	cottony =1
1a2=2	3a4=1	velvety = 2
1a3=2	3a5=1	granular = 3
2a2=2	4a2=1	
3a2=2	4a3=1	
3a3=2	4a4=1	
3a4=2	4b4=1	
4a2=2	4b5=1	
	3b6=2	
	4a6=2	
	4b6=2	
	4b7=2	
	4b8=2	
	4C5=2	
	4c6=2	
	4c7=2	
	4c8=2	
	4d8=3	
	5b5=2	
	5b6=2	
	5b8=2	
	5c4=2	
	5c5=2	
	5c6=2	
	5c7=2	
	5c8=2	
	6c7=2	
	6c8=2	
	5d5=3	
	5d6=3	
	5d7=3	
	5d8=3	
	5e7=3	
	5e8=3	
	5f8=3	
	6d6=3	
	6d7=3	
	6d8=3	
	6e7=3	
	6e8=3	
	6f5=3	
	6f8=3	
	7f8=3	
	8d8=3	
	8f8=3	
	11f8=3	

PL 1527/14		<i>T. interdigitale</i>	1 white	1a1	2 mustard yellow	3b6	2 velvety
PL 1596/15		<i>T. interdigitale</i>	2 yellowish white	1a2	1 corn/ (golden) wheat	4b5	2 velvety
PL 2421/14		<i>T. interdigitale</i>	1 white	1a1	2 golden	4c6	2 velvety
PL 2423/15		<i>T. interdigitale</i>	1 white	1a1	2 golden	4c6	2 velvety
PL 2808/15		<i>T. interdigitale</i>	2 yellowish white/pa	2a2	2 chamcis	4c5	1 cottony
PL 2882/15		<i>T. interdigitale</i>	1 white	1a1	2 topaz	5c5	1 cottony
SK 1253/16		<i>T. interdigitale</i>	1 white	1a1	3 golden brown	5d7	2 velvety
SK 1631/16		<i>T. interdigitale</i>	1 white	1a1	3 yellowish brown	5e8	1 cottony
SK 1803/16		<i>T. interdigitale</i>	1 white	1a1	1 oxide yellow	5c7	2 velvety
SK 3079/16		<i>T. interdigitale</i>	1 white	1a1	1 pale yellow	4a3	1 cottony
SK 3523/15		<i>T. interdigitale</i>	2 yellowish white	4a2	3 english red	8d8	1 cottony
SK 3747/17		<i>T. interdigitale</i>	2 yellowish white	3a2	1 light yellow	4a4	1 cottony
SK 965/16		<i>T. interdigitale</i>	2 yellowish white	4a2	2 chamcis	4c5	2 velvety
CCF 6572	CLIS 1062/17	<i>T.</i>	1 white	1a1	3 golden brown	5d7	3 granular
CCF 6573	CLIS 1182/16	<i>T.</i>	1 white	1a1	3 cognac	6e7	3 granular
CCF 6574	CLIS 2548/16	<i>T.</i>	1 white	1a1	3 cinnamon brown	6d6	3 granular
CCF 6576	CLIS 5116/16	<i>T.</i>	2 yellowish white	3a2	3 light brown	6d8	2 velvety
CCF 6578	CLIS 7172/15	<i>T.</i>	2 yellowish white	3a2	2 popeian yellow	5c6	3 granular
CCF 6579	CLIS 985/17	<i>T.</i>	1 white	1a1	3 yellowish brown	5d8	3 granular
CCF 6580	D 303/15	<i>T.</i>	2 yellowish white	4a2	3 reddish brown/ caput n	8f8	3 granular
CCF 6581	D 488/15	<i>T.</i>	1 white	1a1	3 golden brown	5d7	3 granular
CCF 6582	D 749/16	<i>T.</i>	2 yellowish white	3a2	3 honey yellow	5d6	2 velvety
CCF 6584	ME 742/15	<i>T.</i>	1 white	1a1	2 oxide yellow	5c7	2 velvety
CCF 6585	ME 940/15	<i>T.</i>	1 white	1a1	3 violet brown	11f8	3 granular
CLIS 265/17		<i>T.</i>	1 white	1a1	3 dark yellow/ orange br	4d8	1 cottony
CLIS 3796/16		<i>T.</i>	2 yellowish white/pa	2a2	3 cognac	6e7	2 velvety
CLIS 4666/16		<i>T.</i>	1 white	1a1	2 brownish orange	6c8	2 velvety
CLIS 5937/17		<i>T.</i>	1 white	1a1	3 dark brown	7f8	3 granular
CLIS 6134/15		<i>T.</i>	1 white	1a1	3 dark brown	7f8	3 granular
CLIS 845/17		<i>T.</i>	2 yellowish white	4a2	3 honey yellow	5d6	3 granular
CLIS 9193/16		<i>T.</i>	2 yellowish white	3a2	3 yellowish brown	5d8	2 velvety
D 159/16		<i>T.</i>	1 white	1a1	3 golden brown	5d7	1 cottony
D 374/15		<i>T.</i>	1 white	1a1	3 raw sienna	6d7	3 granular
D 374/16		<i>T.</i>	1 white	1a1	3 brownish grey	6f8	3 granular
D 873/17		<i>T.</i>	2 yellowish white/pa	2a2	3 cinnamon brown	6d6	3 granular
DMF 1146/15		<i>T.</i>	1 white	1a1	2 yolk yellow	4b8	3 granular
DMF 3745/14		<i>T.</i>	2 yellowish white	3a2	2 greyish orange	5b5	3 granular
L 431/16		<i>T.</i>	1 white	1a1	3 yellowish brown	5d8	3 granular
L 45/16		<i>T.</i>	1 white	1a1	3 cognac	6e7	2 velvety
ME 1014/15		<i>T.</i>	2 yellowish white	4a2	3 reddish brown/ caput n	8f8	3 granular
ME 721/14		<i>T.</i>	1 white	1a1	3 rust brown	6e8	3 granular
ME 991/15		<i>T.</i>	1 white	1a1	2 brass/brazen yellow	4c7	1 cottony
SK 1851/16		<i>T.</i>	1 white	1a1	3 linoleum brown	5e7	2 velvety
SK 2873/15		<i>T.</i>	1 white	1a1	3 cognac	6e7	1 cottony
SK 307/16		<i>T.</i>	2 yellowish white	3a2	2 popeian yellow	5c6	3 granular
SK 3354/14		<i>T.</i>	2 yellowish white	3a2	2 chamcis	4c5	1 cottony
SK 3708/14		<i>T.</i>	2 yellowish white	3a2	2 topaz	5c5	1 cottony
SK 571/16		<i>T.</i>	2 yellowish white	4a2	3 raw umber	5f8	3 granular
SK 73/15		<i>T.</i>	1 white	1a1	3 light brown	6d8	3 granular
CCF 6599	SK 3253/16	<i>T. indotineae</i>	2 pastel yellow	3a4	2 oxide yellow	5c7	1 cottony

¹ Komerup A. Wanscher JH. *Methuen Handbook of Colour*. Methuen & Co. Ltd.: 1967.